

QA4EO WP 2230

GROUND-BASED INSTRUMENT CALIBRATION

1 Introduction

This work package dealt with the traceable retrieval of aerosol optical depth (AOD) from narrowband solar filter radiometers. A precision filter radiometer (PFR) from PMOD/WRC was calibrated and characterised in the laboratory. The retrieval of AOD was then performed using solar irradiance measurements in conjunction with top of the atmosphere solar spectra to calculate the atmospheric transmission. This methodology was then compared to the traditional Langley-based method.

Additionally, a CIMEL sunphotometer from AERONET-Europe was characterised in the laboratory for spectral responsivity and angular response, in view of validating the measurements of radiance and irradiance using traceable measurements to the SI.

Finally, a field campaign was performed at the AERONET-Europe calibration site at Observatoire de Haute Provence to perform collocated measurements with a travel standard PFR, to provide traceability of the AERONET-Europe network to the WMO reference operated at PMOD/WRC.

2 D.2.2.3-1: Report on the laboratory characterisation and calibration of one reference PFR

The reference PFR-98-N-001 has been calibrated, in term of defining the spectral responsivity of the filterradiometer, 3 times in the period 2019-2021. Once at PMOD/WRC and once at the German Metrology Institute (Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, PTB) within the project EMPIR MAPP.

The calibration at PMOD/WRC involves the ATLAS tuneable laser system, a ns-pulsed Optical Parametric Oscillator (OPO) system (EKSPLA NT242), for the determination of the relative spectral responsivity while the irradiance scale is established from measurements in front of an irradiance standard, specifically a lamp type FEL calibrated at PTB. The wavelength of the output radiation was measured directly by an LSA (Laser Spectrum Analyser) with an uncertainty of a few picometer. The combined expanded relative uncertainty of this calibration primarily due to the uncertainty of the irradiance standard and secondarily due to the geometry and corrections for the non-linear behaviour of PFR in the pulsed radiations was of the order of 3%.

The latest calibration at PTB (2021) was done on the upgraded TUnable Lasers In Photometry (TULIP) setup based on a ps-OPO laser system. Similarly, the wavelength of the output radiation was measured directly by an LSA. However, the reference detector measuring the output irradiance, is a calibrated 3-element trap detector equipped with a calibrated aperture with uncertainty less than 0.2% ($k=2$).

In this report we present the final results with the lowest uncertainty achieved at the PTB facilities. The spectral responsivity was measured for the 4 PFR channels in the range 300 nm- 1030 nm, the spectral range of the high sensitivity of the silicon detectors of the instrument. The normalized responsivities of the four PFR channels are presented in Figure 1. The integrated responsivity or calibration factor in $mV/(W/m^2)$ along with the uncertainty, centroid wavelength and band pass as Full width at half maximum (FWHM) of each channel are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Centroid wavelength (λ_c) and band pass as FWHM, integrated spectral responsivity and uncertainty for the four PFR channels obtained from the laboratory calibrations at PTB.

Channel	λ_c /nm	FWHM/ nm	Integrated Responsivity 2021/ (mV nm/(Wm ⁻²))	Expanded combined relative uncertainty/(%) Responsivity
1	862.96	5.16	3468.0	0.13
2	500.81	4.69	1944.2	0.17
3	412.01	4.39	1998.0	0.19
4	367.62	3.70	3307.4	0.25

Figure 1: Left panels: Normalized spectral responsivity of the 4 channels of PFR-98-N-001 measured in 2021 at PTB in logarithmic scale as a function of wavelength offset from the centroid wavelength λ' . Right panels: Measured spectral responsivity in linear scale along with an approximated trapezoid filter function (gray lines).

The uncertainty of the laboratory calibration is better than 0.25 % and therefore comparable to a Langley calibration. However, to be used for aerosol optical depth retrieval in an independent SI-traceable schema high resolution SI-traceable top-of-atmosphere (TOA) spectra are needed. Three different top-of-atmosphere spectra QASUMEFTS [Gröbner *et al.*, 2017], TSIS-1 HSRs [Coddington *et al.*, 2021] and ATLAS [Thuillier *et al.*, 2003] have been used and convolved with the relative filter responsivities to provide the TOA irradiance of the PFR $I_0^{\text{QASUMEFTS}}$, I_0^{TSIS} and I_0^{ATLAS} in W/m^2 respectively. These values are compared (Table 2) with the TOA irradiance originating from the calibration of the PFR against the WMO AOD reference the PFR-Triad. An excellent agreement has been found for all four channels to better than 0.36 % when the QASUMEFTS and TSIS-1 HSRs TOA spectra are used while the uncertainties are comparable to the Langley transferred calibration with the exception of the 368 nm channel.

Table 2: TOA solar irradiance values measured with PFR-98-N-001 (I_0^{L}) and the selected TOA spectra weighted with the responsivities measure I_0^{TSIS} , $I_0^{\text{QASUMEFTS}}$, I_0^{ATLAS} along with their percentage differences $I_0 - I_0^{\text{L}}$. The combined expanded relative uncertainties (U) of TOA irradiances are shown in parenthesis next to the values.

λ_c (nm)	I_0^{L} Wm^{-2} (U/%)	I_0^{TSIS} Wm^{-2} (U/%)	$I_0^{\text{QASUMEFTS}}$ Wm^{-2} (U/%)	I_0^{ATLAS} Wm^{-2} (U/%)	$I_0^{\text{TSIS}} - I_0^{\text{L}}$ (%)	$I_0^{\text{QASUMEFTS}} - I_0^{\text{L}}$ (%)	$I_0^{\text{ATLAS}} - I_0^{\text{L}}$ (%)
367.62	4.478 (0.75)	4.428 (2.60)	4.468 (1.57)		-1.12	-0.22	
412.01	7.595 (0.71)	7.580 (1.00)	7.606 (1.22)		-0.20	0.14	
500.80	8.960 (0.73)	8.957 (0.62)		8.909 (3.48)	-0.03		-0.57
863.02	5.002 (0.69)	4.984 (0.60)		5.094 (3.50)	-0.36		1.84

Detailed information on the methodology can be found in: Natalia Kouremeti, Saulius Nevas, Stelios Kazadzis, Julian Gröbner, Philipp Schneider and Kerstin Schwind, SI-traceable solar irradiance measurements for aerosol optical depth retrieval. **Natalia Kouremeti et al 2022 Metrologia in press <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ac6cbb>**.

3 D.2.2.3.2: Report on the laboratory characterisation and calibration of one master CIMEL from Aeronet-Europe

3.1 Spectral Responsivity calibration

The characterisation and calibration of CIMEL #1270 from LOA, AERONET-Europe, was done partly within the project EMPIR MAPP. The spectral responsivity calibrations were performed at the TULIP facility at PTB, in Braunschweig, Germany. The spectral response functions of all channels were measured and the calibration

factors were then compared to the calibration factors retrieved from a Langley-plot campaign held at MaunaLoa in March 2022. The high-resolution solar spectrum TSIS-HSRS was used for this purpose. Figure 2 shows the spectral response of the channel at 500 nm.

The calibration factors retrieved from the laboratory calibration were compared to the recent calibration performed at MaunaLoa using the Langley-plot technique. As shown in Figure 3, the differences are within $\pm 2\%$ for all channels, with the exception of the two shortest channels at 340 nm and 380 nm, where the differences are slightly higher.

Figure 2 Spectral responsivity of CIMEL #1270 for the 500 nm channel. Upper figure shows the filter function in log-scale, while the bottom figure shows the same responsivity in linear scale, as well as the solar spectrum used to calculate the calibration factor for this channel.

Figure 3 Ratio of the calibration factors retrieved from the laboratory calibration, relative to the calibration obtained from the Langely-plot calibration at MaunaLoa in March 2022. The blue dots are the Si-channels, while the red dots are for the InGaAs channels. The gray dot is for the 937 nm channel, where the Langely-plot is uncertain due to the strong atmospheric water vapour absorption.

The differences between the two methods are still too large to be used equivalently. More work within EMPIR MAPP will be undertaken to understand and potentially resolve these differences.

3.2 Field of view characterisation

The field of view was characterised at the Angular Response Facility of PMOD/WRC. The retrieval of the solid angle of the angular field of view of Cimel #1270 was obtained from 2-D scans, as shown in Figure 4:

Figure 4 Left panel: Field of view measurement of the 440 nm channel of Cimel #1270. Right panel: same measurements, but shown in contour mode.

The solid angle retrieved from these measurements allows to relate the direct irradiance measurements to the radiance measurements. This is important, since the inversion procedure to retrieve aerosol optical properties from the direct irradiance and radiance measurements can be significantly improved when the uncertainties of both calibrations are better constrained.

Further work is being performed in collaboration with LOA and NASA, AERONET to characterize the solid angle of additional CIMELs to obtain more statistics on this instrument characteristic.

4 D2.2.3.3: Report of the OHP campaign and statement of applicability of AOD retrieval using laboratory calibrations versus in-situ Langley-based technique

4.1 Report of the OHP campaign

Within the QA4EO project a Precision FilterRadiometer (PFR) traveling standard was installed at the European calibration site of AERONET Europe to provide continuous traceability of aerosol optical depth measurements to the World reference of AOD maintained at Davos through a PFR-Triad. The objective is to homogenise the two global monitoring networks of passive remote sensing of aerosol optical properties, which serve as fiducial reference for satellite derived aerosol properties.

The PFR traveling standard was installed on a solar tracker provided by the laboratory of atmospheric optics (LOA) at the Observatoire de Haute provence (OHP) in southern France (Figure 5) in July 2020 and operated continuously until September 2021. During clear sky periods the measurements of spectral solar irradiance are used to retrieve aerosol optical depth from the master instrument of AERONET-Europe and the PFR. A webpage displayed the real-time comparison between the two instruments and provides a continuous quality control of the measurements (<https://www.pmodwrc.ch/en/world-radiation-center-2/worcc/gaw-pfr/ohp/>).

Figure 5: Platform at the Observatoire de Haute Provence (OHP), France with four CIMEL sunphotometers and the traveling standard PFR on its own solar tracker (right).

The PFR instrument was re-calibrated against the PFR-Triad in the period November 2021- February 2022. The stability of the PFR was within the uncertainty of the reference instruments for all wavelengths with the exception of the 368 nm channel where an unexpected difference of -1.6% was found (Table 3). The dataset of the PFR was re-analyzed and extrapolated to the nearest CIMEL wavelength using the PFR Angstrom exponent when the difference is more than 10 nm. This dataset was compared with the level2 AERONET-Europe data of the master CIMEL (available up to February 2021, accessed on 30.Mar.2022). For that dataset the initial calibration was kept. Comparison results are presented in Figure 6 and Table 4 where the traceability of the two networks based on the WMO criterium (more than 95 % of the compared differences to be within $0.005 \pm 0.001/m$, with m the aerosol airmass) is achieved for the pairs 861/870 nm and 500/500 nm while for the extrapolated wavelengths a satisfactory agreement is achieved only for the 367/380 nm pair. The open access data of the campaign can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6513989>).

Table 3: PFR stability before and after the OHP campaign

Channel centroid wavelength	861.8 nm	500.4 nm	411.3 nm	367.1 nm
Change between calibrations	0.1%	-0.1%	-0.8%	-1.6%

Table 4: Summary of the OHP comparison campaign. AOD differences at the compared wavelength pairs as median and 5th and 95th percentile. Last column percentage of compared values within the WMO limit for traceability between instruments.

Wavelength PFR/CIMEL in nm	AOD Difference			% in WMO limits
	median	5 th percentile	95 th percentile	
861/870	0.002	-0.001	0.006	99.9
500/500	0.004	0.002	0.008	98.2
411/440*	0.009	0.004	0.021	59.7
367/380*	0.007	0.002	0.013	83.2
*Extrapolated with Angstrom exponent, Number of measurements = 3883				

Figure 6: Left panel: AOD difference of OHP Master CIMELs to PFR_N014 at 380 nm, 440 nm, 500 nm and 870 nm for the period 21-Jul-2020 to 28-Feb-2021. The shaded area represents the WMO limit for AOD agreement between two instruments. The AOD difference (dots) is colored based on the probability density function shown in the colored bars on the right panel. Right panel: Normalized probability density functions of the AOD differences for the four wavelengths, approximated by double gaussian distribution functions.

4.2 Statement of applicability of AOD retrieval using laboratory calibrations versus in-situ Langley-based technique

Using the state-of-the-art calibration of PFR-98-N-001 (D.2.2.3-1) the applicability of this method versus the in-situ Langley-based technique represented by the WMO AOD reference the PFR-Triad was investigated using co-located measurements at PMOD/WRC, Davos a few months before the calibration. An overview of this campaign is presented in the following Figure. Figure 7 shows the median differences and the 5th and 95th percentile of the AOD differences against the PFR-Triad for PFR-98-N-001, when using its Langley-transferred calibration and the laboratory one combined with the TOA spectra TSIS-1, QASUMEFTS and ATLAS. The error bars show the uncertainty of AOD due to calibration. The shaded area shows the WMO limit for the campaign. It is evident that the laboratory calibration combined with the TOA spectra TSIS-1, QASUMEFTS give equivalent AOD difference and uncertainties for all available wavelengths when compared to the traditional Langley calibration method.

Figure 7: Panels for the four PFR channels showing the median AOD differences of Langley-based and laboratory calibration in combination with QASUMEFTS, ATLAS and TSIS-1 HSRS TOA spectra to the PFR-Triad (red dots). The coloured squares represent the 5th and 95th percentile of the differences, while the error bars represent the expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) in the AOD from each method accounting for the uncertainty of the TOA spectrum and the PFR calibration. The light blue area represents the adjusted WMO criterium during this campaign to account for the common retrieval algorithm.

5 Report and datasets of Cal/Val field campaigns

No Cal/Val field campaigns took place in phase1.

6 Publications and datasets

Kouremeti, Natalia, Kazadzis, Stelios, Gröbner, Julian, & Goloub, Philippe. (2022). QA4EO-WP2230-D2.2.3.3 Comparison dataset from the OHP campaign (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6513989>.

7 References

Coddington, O. M., E. C. Richard, D. Harber, P. Pilewskie, T. N. Woods, K. Chance, X. Liu, and K. Sun (2021), The TSIS-1 Hybrid Solar Reference Spectrum, *Geophysical Research Letters*, 48(12), e2020GL091709, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL091709>.

Gröbner, J., I. Kröger, L. Egli, G. Hülsen, S. Riechelmann, and P. Sperfeld (2017), The high-resolution extraterrestrial solar spectrum (QASUMEFTS) determined from ground-based solar irradiance measurements, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 10(9), 3375-3383, doi:10.5194/amt-10-3375-2017.

Thuillier, G., M. Hersé, D. Labs, T. Foujols, W. Peetermans, D. Gillotay, P. C. Simon, and H. Mandel (2003), The Solar Spectral Irradiance from 200 to 2400 nm as Measured by the SOLSPEC Spectrometer from the Atlas and Eureca Missions, *Solar Physics*, 214(1), 1-22, doi:10.1023/A:1024048429145.

Natalia Kouremeti et al 2022 Metrologia in press <https://doi.org/10.1088/1681-7575/ac6cbb>